

Unravelling the Threads of War and Displacement in Tehmina Durrani's *Happy Things in Sorrow Times*

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Abstract

This study analyses Tehmina Durrani's novel Happy Things in Sorrow Times, focusing on the intricate portrayal of war and displacement, particularly on children. The research delves into the nuanced ways armed conflict disrupts lives and reshapes identities. Through meticulous analysis, the study aims to unravel the psychological and emotional impact of war on characters. By examining Durrani's treatment of displacement and its effects on personal and cultural identities, this research contributes to understanding the lasting repercussions of conflict on the human psyche. It employs a multidisciplinary approach, integrating literature, psychology, and cultural studies to illuminate the complexities depicted in Durrani's work.

Keywords: War, physical and psychological trauma, moral dilemma, existentialism.

War is a defeat for humanity- **Pope John Paul II**

The impact of war extends its far-reaching and haunting influence over both individuals and societies. The immediate aftermath of armed conflict is marked by widespread destruction, loss of life, and the displacement of countless families. Homes are reduced to rubble, and communities are left shattered. The enduring scars of battle, encompassing both physical and psychological trauma, persist among those directly touched by its brutality. Contemporary writers who delve into the subject of warfare openly express their frustration. Tim O'Brien boldly declares, "War is hell" emphasizing that "this stark description only scratches the surface. For him, war is a complex amalgamation of mystery, terror, adventure, courage, discovery, holiness, pity, despair, longing, and love. It is a paradox, being simultaneously nasty and fun, thrilling and drudgery—a compelling force that moulds some into men while ruthlessly leading others to their demise" (*Things They Carried* 76).

The roots of the modern war novel can be traced back to the 1800s, marked by vivid depictions of historical conflicts like the Battle of Waterloo, the American Civil War, and the Russian Napoleonic Wars. Leo Tolstoy's *War and Peace* stands out as a significant example, embodying the gradual emergence of key themes in war literature, including realism, graphic portrayal of wartime scenes, and exploration of moral dilemmas and existentialism.

However, it was during World War I that war literature truly gained prominence. Henri Barbusse, often credited with the influential 1916 work *Le Feu (Under Fire)*, played a pivotal role in igniting the anti-war literary movement. The aftermath of WWI in the 1920s witnessed a surge in what is now termed the 'War Book Boom' with novels reflecting the lingering impact of trauma, heroism, and anarchism. Some focused intensely on the battlefield, detailing gruesome injuries and the lives of soldiers, such as Sebastian Faulks's *Bird Song* and Erich Maria Remarque's *All Quiet on the Western Front*.

Conversely, other war novels delved into the aftermath, exploring the ripple effects of war, including post-traumatic stress syndrome (PTSS), alienation, and the disruption of societies and families. Works like Pat Barker's *Regeneration* and Virginia Woolf's *Mrs Dalloway* provided a unique perspective, often narrated through the eyes of characters like therapists, mothers, or wives who hadn't experienced war directly but were deeply affected by its consequences. Virginia Woolf, in particular, positioned herself as a valuable contributor, offering a distinct female perspective on war, power, and conflict, a sentiment echoed by many critics.

The evolution of war literature witnessed a shift from a Euro-centric focus in World War I to the emergence of American novelists during World War II, exemplified by Herman Wouk's *The Caine Mutiny*. Authors took varied approaches, with some exploring entire wars over extended periods, while others honed in on specific battles or eras, such as James Hanley's *No Direction* which narrates the story of the Blitz. This diversity in perspective enriched the genre, capturing the intricacies of human experience in times of conflict.

Elizabeth Bowen's *The Heat of the Day* stands as a unique contribution to post-World War II literature. Instead of explicitly depicting the violence of the war, the events unfold against the backdrop of wartime, focusing on people and the war's effects on their lives. This novel offers an alternative framework for war literature, building on the precedent of trauma-centric works.

The aftermath of the Holocaust spurred a surge in post-war novels, a theme that remains popular today with books like *The Tattooist of Auschwitz*. Subsequent conflicts, such as

Vietnam, the Cold War, Iran-Iraq, the Gaza Conflict, Russia-Ukraine War and the post-9/11 War on Terror, have inspired captivating literature exploring various facets of war. Some individuals in war zones now share their experiences through blogs and magazines, like Colby Buzzell's widely popular blog "My War" documenting his time in Iraq.

Commencing in 1979, the Soviet attacks in Afghanistan were military interventions aimed at aiding the communist government against insurgency. The conflict witnessed intense resistance, particularly from mujahideen fighters, resulting in a protracted and harsh war characterized by guerrilla tactics and civilian casualties. Within the broader Cold War context, tensions heightened between the U.S. and the Soviet Union, with the U.S. supporting Afghan resistance efforts. The eventual Soviet withdrawal in 1989 created a power vacuum, triggering internal strife and contributing to the Afghan Civil War and the subsequent rise of the Taliban. The enduring repercussions of these events continue to shape Afghanistan's political, social, and economic landscape.

Soviet attacks confined the lives of the Afghan people to huts, enveloping them in an atmosphere of fear and commotion. Despite attempts at resistance, the Afghan people found themselves helpless against the relentless onslaught. Thunderous blasts became a regular part of their lives, disrupting the peace abruptly. The urgency in the men's voices, shouting "RUN!" while clutching their Kalashnikovs, echoed the constant terror. Even as the chaos ensued, the realization set in that they were running from the looming threat of the Soviets. The call to "prepare for battle!" marked moments of heightened tension, with tanks rolling in, Kalashnikovs crackling from above, and artillery blasting from below. Dynamite explosions punctuated the relentless attacks.

The Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in 1979 reshaped the lives of the native people, erasing distinctions between humans and animals as both were subjected to the same turmoil. The psychological impact of the continuous blasts became ingrained in the collective consciousness, turning the sound of explosions into a hauntingly common dream. Afghan children bore the brunt of trauma induced by the war, and the echoes of explosions replaced the sounds of daily life. Despite the natives' valiant efforts with limited resources, their struggle proved futile against the superpower. Afghanistan stood alone, receiving minimal support even in its hour of need. Even neighbouring Pakistan, acting on American instructions, assisted Afghan refugees by providing them with US milk for survival. Sincerity seemed to be lacking within Afghanistan, leaving its people to fight a solitary battle against Russian troops.

The 1989 Soviet withdrawal from Afghanistan marked the end of the prolonged foreign occupation, stirring varied interpretations of its significance. Contrary to perceptions of a Soviet defeat or a strategic shift, a closer examination revealed a more complex reality. Influenced by a mix of political, military, economic, and domestic factors, the withdrawal was not necessarily an act of desperation. Despite facing challenges, the Soviet Union retained the capacity to control key areas. However, the decision to withdraw was carefully weighed, with the Gorbachev leadership choosing an exit over a prolonged occupation.

Gorbachev introduced a fresh approach to improve the struggling Soviet Union. Unfortunately, the war in Afghanistan didn't align with his plan, Perestroika, and it damaged the Soviet Union's reputation in the West. When they chose to exit Afghanistan, their goal was to demonstrate to the world that they could resolve conflicts peacefully. But strangely, this move made the People's Democratic Party of Afghanistan (PDPA) regime in Afghanistan look more legitimate, and it caused problems for the resistance groups who were against them. Even though the Soviet Union left, Afghanistan was still stuck in a conflict, and people were unsure about what would happen next. There were questions about the Soviet Union's big plans for the region, their goals, and how they would get along with nearby countries. So, even though they left, it wasn't the end of their involvement in the area.

Following the Soviet withdrawal from Afghanistan, a tumultuous decade unfolded. The unprepared Afghan population plunged into internal strife, igniting a brutal civil conflict. Despite declaring victory in the 1979-1989 war, mounting tensions and a grim reality of "Everyone is killing everyone" characterized the post-war period. Exploiting the chaos, warlords exacerbated conditions, prompting a group of psychologically scarred students, referred to as the Taliban, to rise against them. Seen as saviours, the Taliban instilled hope, bringing peace to southern Afghanistan and confronting warlords in the north. Through disarming the population, eliminating crime, and restoring peace, they emerged as transformative figures in a nation scarred by war. On such story *Happy Things in Sorrow Times* by Tahmina Durrani delves into the heartbreak of Afghanistan, portraying the tragedy of Basrabia, a child whose life is shattered by Russian bombs destroying her home and family. Despite the title not finding clear expression in the narrative, the story unfolds against the backdrop of Afghanistan's tumultuous history-from Russian occupation to Taliban rule and the country's victimhood in American bombings and intrigue.

Durrani is a distinguished war novelist known for her compelling narratives that delve into the complexities of conflict, resilience, and human struggle. Through her insightful and

vivid storytelling, she explores the impact of war on individuals and societies, offering a poignant glimpse into the harsh realities of life in the midst of turmoil. Her works provide a unique perspective on the human experience during times of war, capturing the intricacies of emotions, survival, and the profound transformations that emerge from the crucible of armed conflict. As a war novelist, Durrani's writings reflect a deep understanding of the human condition in the face of adversity, making her a notable voice in the literary exploration of war and its aftermath.

Throughout the novel, Durrani touches on sensitive themes, such as the conversation among children from different countries in a refugee camp. The story unveils the unsettling reality of young individuals recruited by Americans from Muslim nations, trained in Pakistani madrassahs, and sent to fight against the Soviets in Afghanistan. The girls in the story reflect on the aftermath of the Soviet retreat, realizing that feeling used and discarded contributed to the emergence of terrorism and subsequent wars.

The central character, Basrabia, navigates the story as an endearing child who abruptly realizes her world has changed with the death of her mother. Seeking refuge with another Afghan family and later attending a school in Peshawar, Basrabia grows up among a diverse group of refugees. Durrani attempts to portray these characters with a touch of whimsy, capturing the bewildering wonder of the world as seen through a child's eyes. However, the execution falls somewhat short, leaving an impression that seems slightly disjointed.

Basrabia is depicted as a 'weird' character, childlike and wide-eyed, with the habit of skipping instead of walking. The narrative suggests a somewhat hysterical and slightly insane persona, reminiscent of *Alice in Wonderland*. Durrani's language, especially in English, reflects a sporadic quality, exhibiting occasional skips and muddles in punctuation, prompting inquiries about her language proficiency.

As the story progresses, it unexpectedly shifts towards a love story, or something akin to it. Basrabia, who has yearned for her childhood friend throughout the narrative, is eventually directed to 'look after her children' in a traditional gender role, despite her valiant journey through horrors. The narrative concludes with the protagonist still skipping, leaving the reader with a sense of continuity in the character's eccentricity.

The psyche delves into the unconscious mind, revealing the true cause of most behaviour. Abnormality, asserts Durrani in *Happy Things in Sorrow Times* stems more from psychological effects than physical ones. Trauma, being unexpected and uncontrollable, has

profound psychological repercussions. Basrabia, born into chaos, witnesses Afghanistan engulfed in a proxy war, cursing her daily existence, “Cursing everything in the world” (16).

The Soviet attack on her home exacerbates Basrabia’s internal conflict, reflecting Freud’s concept of disturbance in the Id i.e “Rather than living our lives, we are ‘lived’ by unknown and uncontrollable forces.” (*The Ego and the Id*). Hallucinations blur reality, and psychological changes unfold, marked by her past haunting her constantly. Associating every event with her family, she adheres to their teachings for guidance. Her psychological struggle is mirrored in her erratic behaviour, simultaneously reflecting both happiness and sadness: “Made it impossible for anyone to know whether she was happy or sad” (Durrani 20). As Freud rightly said: “Life, as we find it, is too hard for us; it brings us too many pains, disappointments and impossible tasks. In order to bear it we cannot dispense with palliative measures... There are perhaps three such measures: powerful deflections, which cause us to make light of our misery; substitutive satisfactions, which diminish it; and intoxicating substances, which make us insensible to it.”(*Civilization and Its Discontents*)

The novel’s title, “*Happy Things in Sorrow Times*,” encapsulates the dichotomy of joy and sorrow in Basrabia’s life. The trauma of the Soviet army transforms her, prompting abnormal behaviour in the vast desert, as seen through her conversations with a cactus. Sher Khan changing her name triggers a loud outburst, highlighting her psychological turmoil. Basrabia’s abnormal behaviour is a reaction to the societal norms surrounding her.

Her dreams turn into a battleground for her psyche, echoing Freud: “Properly speaking, the unconscious is the real psychic; its inner nature is just as unknown to us as the reality of the external world, and it is just as imperfectly reported to us through the data of consciousness as is the external world through the indications of our sensory organs.” (*The Interpretation of Dreams*). The recurring bomb blasts in her dreams symbolize her psychological entrapment, hindering any progress. Hallucinations of Sher Khan persist, revealing her attachment and inability to overcome the trauma, even as a refugee.

Further Durrani masterfully unveils the intricate interplay between external events and Basrabia’s profound psychological changes, laying bare the impact of trauma on the human psyche. Engaging in conversations with a mouse, crow, and bug, Basrabia named them Sher Khan, perceiving them to speak like humans—a manifestation of her abnormality. Witnesses questioned her sanity, reinforcing the notion of her psychological trauma. The bug claimed to be Sher Khan, adding to her hallucinations. People in the refugee camp attempted to awaken Basrabia’s consciousness, pointing out her lagging behind and talking to herself, indirectly

addressing her madness. They confronted her with reality, highlighting her psychological disturbance.

Basrabia, deeply affected by the Russian attack on Afghanistan, connected ordinary activities, like a cat catching a mouse, to her traumatic past. Her screams exposed the turmoil within her psyche. Confronted with the need to confront reality, she grappled with her struggles, yet the camp ridiculed her, oblivious to the intricacies of her condition. Choosing illusion over reality, a coping mechanism to ease the pain of Sher Khan's absence, marked her psychological shift, leading society to label her as mad, subjecting her to mockery and disrespect. Her ongoing battle with psychological trauma was evident as a crow vanished into the sky. "Basrabia wished she could vanish too" (Durrani 61). The madness and abnormality stemmed from separation—from family and, more poignantly, from Sher Khan. Her constant reflection on the past, as she admitted, "I'm thinking, I'm thinking" (60), disturbed fellow refugees with her unusual behavior. "All the refugees, old and young, watched her with their mouths and eyes wide open" (60). Despite everyone in the camp branding her as mad: "You are mad" (64). Basrabia clung to her dress, crafted by her deceased mother, believing it would help her mother find her. It was a manifestation of her psychological struggle to accept the traumatic reality. When asked to change her dress in *Another Chance*, Basrabia's refusal, "I can't take it off! My Moreh won't be able to find me without it" (67), further illuminated her psychological distress. Every utterance and action underscored her psychological trauma and the struggle to overcome it. Encountering an artificial flower, Basrabia remarked, "Yes, it's better than a real one because it never dies" (75), reinforcing her preference for illusions. Despite her improved surroundings, she remained fixated on the death of her parents and Sher Khan's absence, unable to move forward due to the enduring effects on her psychology. Basrabia's sleep patterns served as a revealing mirror to her psychological state, haunted by nightmares of bomb blasts that disrupted everyone's rest. Sharing her nightly ordeal, she confessed, "The sounds of bombs explode in my head every night. I wake everyone up" (Durrani 76), indicating a pressing need for psychological therapy and intervention.

This underscored an underlying issue with her psychology, aligning with Freud's view that dreams reflect the unconscious mind i.e "dream is the dreamer's own psychical act" (*The Interpretation of Dreams*). Every action she took seemed intertwined with her past-Afghanistan, parents, Russian attacks, Tor Gul, and Sher Khan. The overwhelming emotions and memories associated with these elements remained insurmountable. In school, her constant

connection to her past, driven by the traumatic injury and its psychological impact, manifested in unusual activities.

In Geography class, while others studied the map of India, Basrabia fixated on something else. When asked, a classmate explained: “She’s looking at Afghanistan’s border with Russia, Ma’am, so that she knows from where the enemy attacked” (84). Similarly, in a Biology lecture, she gazed at a drawing of the human heart, associating it with Sher Khan’s emotions without Tor-Gul and his family. Her mental absence in the class reflected her fixation on Afghanistan and Sher Khan.

Illustrations throughout the novel depicted the psychological effects on Basrabia, with titles like ‘Moreh’s Dress - Basrabia’s Forever’ (19), ‘Illusions - The Mouse, The Crow, and The Cat’ (58), ‘Another Chance for a Wounded Heart’ (65), and ‘Basrabia with Sher Khan in Every Class’ (86). These images underscored the pervasive madness within Basrabia. Despite numerous therapy sessions, the reports consistently revealed “No Progress” (89).

Sher Khan’s life underwent a profound transformation due to psychological trauma inflicted by the loss of his entire family in a Russian attack. Since boyhood, fueled by a burning desire for revenge, he became the “Tiger king” of Afghanistan, leading the Taliban government. The psychological trauma shaped his aggressive actions, turning him into a powerful figure who sought revenge against the Russians, ultimately defining his role in the Afghan war.

Similarly, Basrabia, affected by the same issues of aggressiveness, nightmares, and hopelessness resulting from psychological trauma, lived her life with a slight shift toward seeking a cure. Both Sher Khan and Basrabia’s lives were fundamentally altered by trauma, steering them onto paths filled with disturbance and challenges. Without the traumatic events, they could have been very different individuals.

Basrabia, during her stay in Afghanistan, acknowledged that the extensive therapy at Another Chance confirmed the incurable nature of her condition (153). Even she realized that physical changes were possible, but her psychological state remained unaltered. Her friend, Hoor, advised her to return to her conscious self and embrace the beauty of the world. However, Basrabia’s response, “I truly wish to follow your advice and forget Sher Khan, the Taliban, and Afghanistan. Hoor, but I am magnetically pulled to them against my will” (117), emphasized that her psychological condition wasn’t within her conscious control.

The final paragraph of her letter provided insight into her psychological struggles, displaying a remarkable level of maturity and clarity that eventually prompted her to confess

her psychological trauma. Basrabia articulated a profound truth: “The initiators of war may have removed the bullets from their guns, resolved their differences or achieved their designs, and ended their wars, but children who lived through those violent, tragic and diabolical times will never forget” (119). Basrabia, an invisible child of war, acknowledged that while wars might conclude for adults, the psychological impact endures for children like her. She recognized the lasting scars of war, emphasizing the persistent psychological trauma faced by children who have experienced such violent and tragic times.

The invisible children of Afghanistan faced a similar fate, living unheard in a society dominated by war violence. Left orphaned, they navigated a world filled with fear and insecurity, constantly exposed to attacks and blasts by powerful forces. Their psychological trauma, stemming from the loss of family and the violence around them, took a toll on their lives, leaving them voiceless victims in a war-ravaged homeland. Every day, the psychological trauma inflicted on these children in Afghanistan takes a toll, silently eroding their well-being.

Thus through the exploration of war and displacement in Durrani’s *Happy Things in Sorrow Times* reveals a rich tapestry of human experiences woven with the threads of conflict. Through her narrative prowess, adeptly captures the multifaceted impact of war on individuals, particularly the vulnerable demographic of children. The novel serves as a poignant testament to the enduring psychological and emotional consequences of armed conflict, shedding light on the intricate ways in which war disrupts lives and reshapes identities. Through a multidisciplinary lens encompassing literature, psychology, and cultural studies, this research has unveiled the nuanced layers of Durrani’s portrayal of war and its aftermaths. The characters in novel become vessels through which she explores the lasting repercussions of conflict on personal and cultural identities. The psychological trauma, displacement-induced struggles, and the profound changes in the characters’ lives serve as a mirror reflecting the harsh realities of war.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the relevance of Durrani’s work in fostering a deeper understanding of the human condition amidst conflict. By unravelling the threads of war and displacement, this research contributes to the broader discourse on the enduring impact of armed conflict on the human psyche. *Happy Things in Sorrow Times*, with its evocative storytelling, serves not only as a literary work but also as a valuable source for comprehending the complexities of war-induced trauma.

As we conclude this exploration, it becomes evident that *Happy Things in Sorrow Times* stands as a compelling narrative that invites readers to empathize with the profound struggles

faced by individuals caught in the tumult of war. Through the lens of Durrani's characters, we witness the resilience of the human spirit in the face of adversity and the indomitable will to find moments of happiness amidst sorrow. The threads of war and displacement, meticulously unravelled in this study, contribute to a deeper understanding of the human cost of conflict, urging us to contemplate the significance of empathy and collective efforts in fostering a more compassionate world.

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